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Future of Japanese Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in Bangladesh

1.ABSTRACT

Japan has been Bangladesh's "single largest donor" since Bangladesh and Japan first established diplomatic ties in February 1972. It is questionable if Bangladesh's sustainability accomplishments have benefited from such significant official development support, nevertheless (ODA). Bangladesh barely receives a little share of total Japanese investments and international trade, notwithstanding the scale of Japan's economic assistance to Bangladesh. Despite having many competitive advantages, Bangladesh has a sizable trade deficit in its trade with Japan. Investment in this nation is still fairly low, similar to Bangladesh's efforts to draw Japanese investors and businesspeople with a package of incentives and better infrastructure. In spite of Japan's acknowledgment of Bangladesh's strategic significance in a changing Asia and its determination to help the country improve its approach to global competitiveness, the country's reputation abroad is tarnished by poor governance and political instability. It is critical to acknowledge the challenges that Japan and Bangladesh face in their bilateral relationship in light of this and to assess the significance of their economic cooperation.

2.KEYWORDS

Foreign Direct Investment, Future, Japan, Relation, Bangladesh

3.INTRODUCTION

It is regrettable to say that the seven countries that make up the South Asian Association for Regional Cooperation (SAARC), also known as "South Asia"—India, Pakistan, Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Nepal, Bhutan, and the Maldives—have not been able to keep up with the changing trends in the Asia-Pacific region (Nobende, 2002). This is evident from the way Japan's diplomacy has given China and South Korea precedence over the ASEAN member countries (ASEAN). South Asia hasn't always received the highest priority from Japan. With the exception of a few businesses that have recently expressed interest in the region, especially India, neither the Japanese government nor intellectual circles have shown a lot of interest in South Asia (Jain, 1996). But

starting in the early 1990s, Japan started to devote more attention to this region. When most South Asian countries implemented economic liberalization policies, there seemed to be a "promising vista" for cooperation between Japan and South Asia (Moni, 2004). Japan seems willing to continue assisting the South Asian nations in the post-September 11 age in the interest of increasing regional solidarity, allowing them to cooperatively contribute to the global partnership by strengthening communication and understanding of each other's national security concerns. This ambition is clearly demonstrated by Japan's decision to designate a seasoned diplomat (Yasushi Akashi) as a special representative to assist the Sri Lankan peace process.

In especially with reference to Bangladesh, it is significant to note that Japan contributed significantly to the fight for Bangladesh's independence in 1971. (Jalal, 2001). Since the two nations' diplomatic relations were established in February 1972, Japan has provided official development assistance (ODA) to the 145 million people who call the nation home. Bangladesh has always regarded Japan in "high respect," and it has pledged to help it pursue reasonable goals in international relations (Japan Times, 21 August 2000). Therefore, the basis of the bilateral relationship in the political and diplomatic arenas has been mutual interests and shared values. The economic differences in the bilateral trade and foreign direct investment (FDI) markets of the two nations should not be disregarded, though. Bangladesh's contribution to Japanese foreign investment and commerce is basically non-existent, notwithstanding the amount of Japan's ODA to Bangladesh. Despite having many competitive advantages, Bangladesh has consistently experienced a sizable trade deficit with Japan. Little has actually changed in this sector, despite the fact that it has made every effort to attract Japanese investors and entrepreneurs by offering a package of incentives and by enhancing the investment environment. Despite Japan's recognition of Bangladesh's strategic importance in a changing Asia (Horiguchi, 2004) and its greatest assistance to the nation, Bangladesh's negative reputation abroad due to poor governance and political instability weighs heavily against all of its positive but improperly projected standpoints. Given that Bangladesh places a high priority on economic development and that Japan bases much of its foreign policy on economic considerations, it is crucial to think through the potential economic effects of a cooperative relationship between the two countries.

4.LITERATURE REVIEW

4.1 Foreign Direct Investment: A brief idea

A long-term management holding (10 percent or more of the voting stock) in a business in the new era of globalization, military power and traditional ideas of security are being redefined more and more to take into account the significance of resource mobilization and risk-sharing, economic assistance and development cooperation, foreign investment and technology transfer, trade and business, environment and sustainability, etc. For instance, the Asia-Pacific region has seen exceptional economic growth, and within this most dynamic region, Japan has not only emerged as a major economic force but also evolved into a highly desired example for many developing economies. Despite the recent stagflation, South Korea, Taiwan, and some countries in Southeast Asia have attained exceptional levels of wealth (Klein, 2002). With the application of measures for economic liberalization and reform, China is advancing economically. Japan has made a major contribution to the Asia Pacific region's economic growth. Despite its present economic depression, Japan, an Asian nation, has moved up to influence changes in the region given its significant geopolitical position there (Doughlas, 2006). The country has also assumed considerable management responsibilities for the global economy over the past few decades.

that conducts business in a nation other than the investor's own is referred to as a "foreign direct investment" when it is purchased with net funds. The balance of payments indicates that it is the sum of equity capital, earnings reinvested, other long-term capital, and short-term capital. This information, which is split down by GDP, shows net inflows of foreign capital into the reporting economy (new investment less withdrawals) (Stiffen, 2018). The expression is frequently used in business contexts to denote a decision to expand operations or buy a significant stake in a foreign company. The expression is not frequently used to describe a single stock investment in a foreign company. FDI is essential to global economic integration because it forges solid, long-lasting linkages between economies. Foreign direct investments (FDIs) are sizeable, long-term investments made into a foreign enterprise by a company or a government. The investment could entail purchasing a material supply, growing a business's reach, or establishing a global presence. Investors in foreign direct investment (FDI) frequently hold controlling positions in domestic businesses or joint ventures and actively participate in their management. China and the United

States have received the majority of FDI during the previous few years. The United States and other OECD countries have historically been the major contributors to FDI outside of their own borders.

Enterprises or governments seeking foreign direct investment often choose target businesses or projects in open economies that have a trained workforce and above average development potential for the investor (FDI). Minimal government regulation is valued frequently as well. FDI frequently entails more than just capital investments. The provision of management, technology, and tools may also be necessary. One of its primary characteristics is the development of effective control over the foreign company, or at the very least, significant influence over its decision-making.

Global Foreign Direct Investment; Source : Economics Help

The net amounts of money associated with FDI are substantial, with over \$1.8 trillion in FDI anticipated to be made in 2021. (Stallion, 2021). After the United States, China, Canada, Brazil, and India were the other top FDI destinations in that year. In terms of FDI outflows, the United States came out on top, followed by Germany, Japan, China, and the United Kingdom.

By examining FDI inflows as a percentage of GDP, one can evaluate how appealing a nation is as a long-term investment location. The Chinese economy is now smaller than the US economy in absolute terms, but as of 2020, FDI as a percentage of GDP in China was 1.7%, as opposed to 1.0% in the US. For smaller, more active economies, such as the Cayman Islands (110%), Hungary (109%), and Hong Kong (34%) (also for 2020), FDI as a percentage of GDP is typically far higher (Faruk, 2021).

It is possible to create a foreign subsidiary or associate firm, buy a controlling interest in an existing foreign company, merge with another international company, or form a joint venture with another foreign company. These are but a few illustrations of the numerous methods in which foreign direct investments can be made.

The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) created guidelines that state that in order for an FDI to establish a controlling stake, the amount of ownership in a company with a foreign base must be at least 10%. Its application is unlimited. In certain situations, acquiring less than 10% of the voting shares of a firm can lead to the development of an actual controlling interest in the company.

Foreign direct investments are typically categorized under the horizontal, vertical, and conglomerate headings.

- With a horizontal FDI, a corporation establishes the same type of business activity abroad that it does at home.
- In a vertical FDI, a business buys a complementing company in a different country, such in the case of an American cell phone provider buying a network of phone stores in China. For instance, a US company may purchase ownership in a foreign company that offers it the raw materials it needs.
- In a conglomerate FDI, a company invests in a foreign enterprise that is unrelated to its principal business. This typically appears as the investment company's lack of past experience in the joint venture's area of expertise.

FDI has the capacity to encourage and maintain economic growth in both the nation making the investment and the recipient nation. On the one hand, developing countries have backed FDI as a way to finance the construction of new infrastructure and the creation of jobs for their domestic labor force. Global firms benefit from FDI, though, because it helps them expand their market

penetration internationally. The fact that FDI is subject to inspection and control by numerous nations, however, amplifies the political risk.

4.2 Foreign Direct Investment Influencing Factors

The following variables have the greatest impact on foreign direct investment because they have a substantial impact on a nation's economy:

- Inflation
- National earnings
- Governmental limitations
- Rates of exchange

The effects of inflation: Other things being equal, it would be predicted that a country's capital account would decline if its inflation rate rose relative to the nations it invested in. Due to the strong local inflation, it is likely that local consumers and businesses would spend more money domestically or invest more abroad, while international investment and exports will decrease.

The effect of national income: Other things being equal, it is assumed that a country's capital account will decline if its national income rises at a rate greater than that of other nations. The consumption of products increases together with the actual income level (adjusted for inflation). Most certainly, a portion of the rise in consumption will be reflected in a rise in the need for foreign investment.

Governmental restrictions' effects: The government of a nation has the power to bar or discourage foreign investment. Such restrictions cause the government to obstruct investment flows. The most frequently employed investment restrictions include fiscal policy changes, intellectual property rights protections, and bureaucratic snarls. In addition to this, a government can limit the amount that can be invested by implementing laws or other restrictions.

Exchange rate effects: Exchange rates are used to determine the worth of one nation's currency in relation to other currencies, allowing for the exchange of currencies to speed up international trade. Most currencies' values can change over time as a result of market and governmental influences. If everything else is equal, a country's capital account balance should drop if its currency starts to appreciate against other currencies. Investment made by that country will cost more than investments made by receiving countries as the currency gains strength.

4.3 Benefits of FDI

The importance of foreign direct investments (FDI) has increased significantly over the past few decades as a result of globalization, which offers the majority of developing countries significant opportunities to achieve faster economic growth through trade and investment. Foreign direct investment (FDI) aids host countries in gaining advanced technology and connecting to global production and trade networks while also supporting foreign investors in making better use of their assets and resources. The importance of foreign direct investments (FDI) has increased significantly over the past few decades as a result of globalization, which offers the majority of developing countries significant opportunities to achieve faster economic growth through trade and investment. Foreign direct investment (FDI) aids host countries in gaining advanced technology and connecting to global production and trade networks while also supporting foreign investors in making better use of their assets and resources. The following are the impacts of FDI on host country economies:

Trade Effects: FDI increases total factor productivity and resource usage efficiency, which fosters economic growth in the host country. It increases the capital stock of the host country, which raises output levels.

Benefits of FDI; Source: Research Gate

Contribution to human capital: FDI significantly boosts the human capital of the countries it invests in. MNEs expand employment prospects, reducing unemployment in the country of origin. For instance, domestic employees might change employers from foreign to domestic ones. By working together with international companies to learn from them, local businesses could increase production.

Effects that Spread: MNEs often have more sophisticated technology, particularly "clean," which is the main factor in their superior productivity. FDI has the advantage of generating significant

technological spill overs in the host countries (Stallion, 2018). Local firms may become more productive if they have access to modern, improved, or more inexpensive intermediate inputs produced by MNE in upstream sectors.

Level of Competition: FDI significantly affects how aggressively enterprises compete in the host country. The presence of MNEs supports economic development by fostering domestic competition, which raises productivity, innovation, lowers prices, and results in more efficient resource allocation.

Management and Government Practice: According to management and government practice, FDI has altered management and corporate governance through the acquisition of local enterprises. MNEs often impose their internal reporting systems, business regulations, and information disclosure policies (Kouchi, 2019). This impact improves organizational effectiveness and the business climate.

4.4 Limitations of FDI

An issue with foreign direct investment is the dangers involved. Investment dividends cannot be guaranteed for the foreseeable future. Due to the fact that the global political environment is also inherently unstable, a firm may lose its investment as soon as it is founded if a seizure or takeover occurs.

Here are a few other negative effects of foreign direct investment.

Crowding out FDI's impact: FDI's impact on the economy of the host nation can either be crowding in or out. The monopoly power that MNEs come to possess over the market is the crowding out effect's main adverse consequence (Kabir, 2006). Crowding out typically results from two factors:

1. When overseas subsidiaries outperform domestic counterparts in terms of productivity and product quality.
2. When they are destroyed due to the superior financial capabilities or anticompetitive practices of their foreign affiliates.

Profit Repatriation: MNEs invest abroad with the main goal of maximizing their earnings, which is known as profit repatriation. The favourable characteristics of these countries, such as their vast natural resources, low cost of labor, or high levels of competence, allow MNEs to increase their

economic performance (Anderson, 2012). MNEs frequently transfer their investment profits to the parent companies' bank accounts in the form of dividends or royalties paid to shareholders in addition to the simple transfer of accumulated profits. They are also able to avoid paying greater taxes by using transfer prices. However, because of these capital outflows, the home country suffers from a negative balance of payments with the host country (Bellini, 2010). As a result, the host countries frequently place limitations on the amounts of profits that MNEs may repatriate in order to minimize balance of payment deficits or dwindling foreign exchange reserves. Such a policy might entice these MNEs to invest their profits in diverse domestic initiatives.

Effect of the Dual Economy: FDI, particularly in developing countries, can lead to them having a dual economy, where one developed sector is dominated by foreign enterprises and the other by homegrown firms. A nation's economic structure changes as a result of an overly reliant developed sector. This developed sector usually has a low labor intensity while exhibiting a high capital intensity (Miller, 2020). The dual economy effect impedes the nations' ability to progress economically because the majority of their population works in an underdeveloped, labour-intensive industry. This effect is noticeable in the majority of oil-rich countries where foreign investments in the oil and gas sector contributed to the resource development while undermining the manufacturing and agricultural sectors.

Environmental Issues: Developing and less developed countries get a large amount of FDI into their natural resource businesses. Most of these countries either have very few restrictions or much laxer ones. Some countries consciously waive or relax their regulatory norms in an effort to attract FDI (Ima, 2019). The solution to these problems is to strengthen the host country's ability to put international environmental norms into practice.

4.5 Conditions for attracting high-quality FDI

Open markets to encourage FDI inflows. Lessen the FDI restrictions. Give domestic and international firms fair, reliable, and convenient operating conditions. These prerequisites ought to cover things like ease of doing business, access to imports, and intellectual property rights protection.

Create an organization to promote investments (IPA). An efficient IPA might look for the best foreign investors and act as a bridge between them and the domestic economy. It should, on the one hand, act as a one-stop shop for the demands that investors make on the host country. On the

other hand, it should act as a booster for the domestic economy of the host nation, encouraging it to create top-notch infrastructure and make qualified workers, technicians, engineers, and managers freely accessible in order to entice such investors (Moran, 2014; Barnes et al., 2015; Harding and Javorcig, 2012). It should also participate in post-investment assistance, taking into account the tangible results from satisfied investors, the potential for reinvestments, and the potential for cluster expansion as a result of following investments.

Targeted businesses and endeavours need to be carefully chosen. Major multinational investors in the host economy may have an impact on supplier location and investment decisions (McKinsey, 2001; Javorcik et al., 2006).

Build the facilities for specialized worker training as well as the local transit choices (airports, ports), reliable energy supply, skilled labor force, and workforce that will attract excellent investors. With the investor, these amenities should be properly planned (Ibid.).

Bolster the domestic economy's links to FDI on the backward side. Allow a variety of direct assistance programs from foreign corporations to domestic businesses, including finance, training, help building up manufacturing lines, management coaching about strategy and financial planning, financing, help with quality control, and introduction to export markets. Allow for the competitive pressure that foreign competitors exert on their domestic suppliers to increase the latter's competitiveness (Rhee et al., 1990). (Javorcik and Spatareanu, 2005; Blalock and Gert).

FDI spillovers into the domestic economy should be encouraged. Görg and Strobl (2005) assert that local companies formed by managers who previously held positions with multinational enterprises are more effective and successful than others. Local business owners may study and imitate their international competitors to learn about contemporary technologies and marketing techniques (Javorcik and Spatareanu, 2005; Boly et al., 2015). When employees move from multinational to local enterprises, similar knowledge and skill transfers take place.

Encourage potential foreign direct investors. Foreign businesses are more open to collaborating with domestic suppliers if they do not already have a wide network of subsidiaries (Amendolagine et al., 2015).

Diaspora investors should be urged to make overseas investments. They are also more likely to network with local companies and promote the globalization of the host country (Boly et al., 2014).

By reforming the domestic financial system, credit availability is increased. By creating a financial system that is favorable to business, local companies can respond to pressures and ideas from foreign rivals, self-select into supplier status, and grow and prosper as a result (Alfaro et al., 2009).

To facilitate communication between local vendors and international customers, establish a vendor development program. With the help of Singapore's Local Industry Upgrading Program (LIUP), local suppliers can get the funding they need to make the necessary upgrades to their facilities. This is done by using purchase agreements with foreign clients. Another case is the Singapore Economic Development Board returning the salary of a manager in a foreign plant who was looking for talent among local suppliers.

Export Processing Zones (EPZs) ought to be planned to act as a springboard for the domestic economy. Avoid EPZ restrictions that limit the creation of alliances with regional suppliers. To assist in vendor selection, establish a secondary industrial zone for local vendors, either as a physical location next to authorized export processing zones or as a legal status allowing for convenient international and domestic connections with, for example, databanks and "marriage counsellors" (Moran et al., 2016).

Reframe the "Who Are Us?" perspective and resolve related problems. "Us" should be understood to refer to the enterprises that are most beneficial to the home economy, regardless of the nationality of their owners. Thus, "Us" refers to the businesses that generate the lowest-priced items, the most competitive exports, and the positions with the highest salaries and levels of competence (Reich, 1990).

Be patient and rely on the ongoing structural reform of the domestic economy. There may be a large influx of investors. Investors in computers, computer peripherals, and data processing systems would come second, followed by those in television and broadcasting systems, thermionic tubes, valves, and transistors. In a similar vein, FDI could aid in diversifying and enhancing domestic output (Amendolagine et al., 2013; Moran, 2014; Barnes et al., 2015).

4.6 FDI in Bangladesh

4.6.1 Current Status of FDI

In the calendar year 2010, Bangladesh attracted USD 913 million in FDI, an increase of 30%. This raises the nation's ranking in the World Investment Report from 119 to 114 out of 141 countries

(WIR). During this time, the manufacturing sector received USD 238 million in foreign investment, the textile and apparel sector USD 145 million, and the leather and leather products sector USD 46 million. The telecom sector received USD 360 million in FDI (The Financial Express, 27 July, 2011). Bangladesh must continue to attract foreign direct investment (FDI) in order to continue developing as a developing country. Ever since winning its independence, Bangladesh has worked to become a country that welcomes FDI. For the purpose of accelerating economic growth, Bangladesh opened its economy in the late 1980s so that it might receive FDI. In order to facilitate and draw in foreign investment, the government formed the Board of Investment (BOI) in 1989. (Mondal, 2003). Additionally, the government steadily relaxed limitations on capital and profit repatriation and opened up nearly all industrial sectors to foreign investment, either on their own or in partnership with local partners. Additionally, the government introduced a number of financial and non-financial incentives, such as tax exemptions for power generation, import duty exemptions for export processing industries, tax holiday schemes for undertaking investment in priority sectors and low development areas, a zero duty rate for the import of capital machinery and spare parts for industries that are entirely export oriented, almost no restrictions on entry and exit mode, and a reduction in burea Since the late 1980s, Bangladesh has been a desirable location for FDI in the South Asian region thanks to all of these advantages and a low labor cost structure.

When compared to preceding decades, Bangladesh's FDI inflow trend rose over the 1980s, and this tendency has continued into the 1990s. Over time, there has been an increase in FDI inflow overall. Total FDI inflows from 1977 to 2010 was USD 8927.9 million, of which USD 4158.63 million came from the period from 2006 to 2010. The yearly FDI reached USD 1086.31 million in 2008, up from USD 7 million in 1977. Sadly, FDI inflows decreased in 2010 and totalled USD 913.32 million (Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department, Bangladesh Bank).

The trend of FDI inflows to Bangladesh between 1996 and 2010 is seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1: FDI inflows in USD in Bangladesh during 1996-2010; Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department of Bangladesh Bank and Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh (1971-2010), Board of Investment.

The FDI inflows during the time are depicted inconsistently in Figure 1. The FDI fell sharply in 1999, and the trend persisted in 2001, 2002, and 2003 for a variety of factors. Foreign investment was inhibited by the period's serious political upheaval, and it required a long time to win back their trust. There were a few other variables that compelled this decline in inflows as well. After that, Bangladesh received some excellent news. From 2003 to 2005, there was a continuous increase in the inflow of FDI. It soared to US\$ 1086.3 million in 2008, fell to US\$ 700.16 in 2009, and then increased once more to US\$ 911.32 in 2010.

4.6.2 FDI Inflows by Components

Figure 2: FDI Inflows (in million USD) by components in Bangladesh during 1996-2010; Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department of Bangladesh Bank and Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh (1971-2010), Board of Investment.

Figure 3: FDI Inflows, in million USD by components in 1996

Figure 4: FDI Inflows, in million USD by components in 2010; Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department of Bangladesh Bank and Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh (1971-2010), Board of Investment.

Three things make up FDI in Bangladesh: equity capital, reinvested earnings, and intra-company loans. These elements have undergone significant change over the past 20 years. Early in 1996, there were only 210 million USD in overall FDI inflows, with reinvested earnings making up the majority of that amount. This pattern persisted through 1998. Then, both the total inflow of FDI and the inflow of FDI by component suddenly start to fall. With the exception of a little rise in 2000, this downward trend persisted until 2003. Following that, the overall inflow increased with some ups and downs. Inflows of total FDI continue to be dominated by the equity capital component. The overall inflows reached an all-time high of \$1100 million in 2008. Figures 3 and 4 clearly show Bangladesh's FDI inflow moving by component. The majority of FDI input to Bangladesh currently consists of equity capital. The percentage of equity capital in overall FDI increased from 30% in 1996 to 57 percent in 2010. Share of reinvested earnings was 53% in 1996, but it fell to 40% in 2010. Contrarily, the percentage of intra-company loans was 17 percent, falling to 3 percent in 2010. This demonstrates that Bangladesh receives a very small net transfer

of resources from other countries. When it comes to the transfer of "hardware" technology, FDI makes a very small impact.

4.6.3 Inflows of FDI by Region (EPZ and non EPZ)

Figure 5: FDI Inflows (in million USD) by area (EPZ and non EPZ) in Bangladesh during 1996-2010; Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department of Bangladesh Bank and Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh (1971-2010), Board of Investment.

Figure 5 shows that between 2001 and 2003, FDI inflows into non-EPZ areas decreased despite an initial rise and sustained continuation. It climbed to USD 800 million in 2004 and this pattern persisted through to 2005. In contrast to the beginning of this era (in 1996), when it was USD 189.3 million, or 82 percent of total inflows, the FDI inflows in Non EPZ areas in 2010 totalled USD 795.15 million, or 87% of total inflows. The FDI inflows were consistently going in the same direction in the EPZ regions.

4.6.4 FDI Inflows by Sectors

A sector-by-sector examination of FDI demonstrates that foreign investors' investment strategies in Bangladesh have changed (Annex Table-3.4). The table illustrates the pattern of foreign direct investment in favour of the power and energy, manufacturing, and telecommunications sectors, while neglecting the agriculture, services, and trade and commerce sectors. The manufacturing industry received the majority of investment in 2005. A key component of this investment was the ready-made garments (RMG) industry's success in the textiles sector. The sectorial movement in FDI for Bangladesh is depicted in the pie chart. The pie chart clearly illustrates how the size of

recent FDI inflows has changed. Manufacturing's losing bastion status for foreign investment is evident from the decline in FDI shares of the industry. On the other side, the telecom industry has been growing recently. The manufacturing sector was no longer the top recipient of FDI in 2008; instead, it was the telecommunications sector. Telecom has become one of the fastest growing industries in Bangladesh's economy as a result of the government's increased efforts to privatize the industry. A big part of this might be attributed to the heightened competitiveness among huge private firms, which has boosted efforts to draw FDI and acquire better and most recent technologies to maximize earnings. Additionally, less foreign direct investment is attracted to the energy industry, which can be attributed to the nation's natural gas reserves. The difficulty in producing electricity in the nation is another problem. The government is frequently forced to "load shed" power due to a lack of production capacity. In order to address the needs of places with higher power usage, it imposes blackouts in areas with low power usage. Because the government lacks the resources to construct power grids and increase the nation's electrical capacity, there are many opportunities for international investment.

Figure 6: FDI Inflows (in million USD) by sectors in Bangladesh during 1996-2010; Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department of Bangladesh Bank and Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh (1971-2010), Board of Investment.

Figure 7: FDI Inflows (in million USD) by sectors in Bangladesh during 1996-2000; Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department of Bangladesh Bank and Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh (1971-2010), Board of Investment.

Figure 8: FDI Inflows (in million USD) by sectors in Bangladesh during 2001-2005; Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department of Bangladesh Bank and Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh (1971-2010), Board of Investment.

Figure 9: FDI Inflows (in million USD) by sectors in Bangladesh during 2006-2010; Source: Survey Report, Statistics Department of Bangladesh Bank and Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh (1971-2010), Board of Investment.

It is evident from Figure 8 and 3.4.4 that there have been significant changes in the percentage of investment in different industries. Telecommunication investment as a proportion was only 2% from 1996 to 2000, but it increased to 21% from 2001 to 2005 and eventually peaked at 43% from 2006 to 2010. On the other hand, from 1996 to 2010, the amount of investment in the gas and petroleum sector significantly decreased. In 1996 to 2000, it was 28%, in 2001 to 2005, 18%, and from 2006 to 2010, just 13%. Additionally, it is extremely concerning that investment in the energy sector has dropped from 12% to barely 3%. The government should carefully examine this issue and take the required action to pinpoint the root causes and correct them in order to enhance the state of our current energy sector.

4.7 Effect of FDI on Bangladesh's economic expansion

An increase in FDI was intended to support domestic investment in the nation and lead to the creation of jobs, income growth, and increased prosperity. Some of the potential direct and indirect effects of FDI are described here.

4.7.1 Direct Effect

We will focus on three problems when analysing the direct effects of FDI in Bangladesh: the balance of payments, job effects, and revenue effects.

Support for Balance of Payments: While FDI encourages capital formation in the nation, it can also put pressure on the balance of payments through profit repatriation. The impact of repatriation remained manageable because Bangladesh's overall foreign investment was relatively negligible. Bangladesh has tried to promote foreign investment in export-oriented businesses in an effort to maintain this pressure within manageable bounds. A total of \$266.01 million in profit, dividends, and royalties related to foreign investment were returned home in FY03, which is about \$70 million more than the net inflow of FDI during the same year. As a result, a nation that lacks capital ends up becoming a net exporter of capital. Of course, in order to determine the net impact of FDI on the balance of payments, it is also required to consider the indirect effects of FDI on the import bill and export income. The effects of FDI on the import bill could be in conflict with one another. It could encourage consumers to spend more money abroad in order to pay for legitimate imports, but it could also result in foreign currency savings through effective import-competitive production.

Employment Situation: It is challenging to provide a clear picture of the impact of FDI on the creation of jobs due to the dearth of data on employment outside of EPZs. To determine the number of jobs held by foreign businesses in the domestic tariff region, FICCI conducted a survey in 2004. According to this poll, 129,549 people—or 0.68 percent of Bangladesh's overall manufacturing employment—were working for foreign companies in the DTA. The consumer goods and apparel industries employed the biggest percentage of employees from overseas companies. About 0.74 percent of the nation's total manufacturing employment—140,050 people, up from about 130,000 in FY03—was located in the EPZs. About 2.7 million jobs, or less than 15% of all manufacturing employment, have been created by foreign enterprises overall (EPZs and domestic tariff area combined). This shows that FDI does not significantly contribute to the creation of jobs in Bangladesh.

In addition to the fact that the job possibilities produced by foreign businesses are minimal, it is significant to consider the type of employment that FDI in Bangladesh produces. The majority of the workforce is employed in low-wage, unskilled positions that have little to no impact on the local economy. This may be especially true of the EPZs, though. Most middle and upper management roles in foreign companies located outside of EPZs are staffed by local experts, and there are more highly compensated, skilled professions with a greater positive impact on the local economy.

Revenue Impact: Foreign investors have the potential to be a significant source of income for their host nations. By increasing public investment, these incomes can support economic and social development. According to estimates, international investors in Bangladesh contribute over \$13.20 million a year to the national coffers³⁹. However, as discussed in Section 2, the too generous incentive packages provided to FDIs frequently result in the loss of significant revenue-generating opportunities. Therefore, it is crucial for policymakers to strike a balance between the goals of promoting a more substantial competitive strength of the economy and their desire to attract and keep foreign investment beyond the tax vacation period, led by the requirement to maximize fiscal revenues.

4.7.2 Indirect Effect

Technology Transfer: A key indicator of impact is the amount of technology transfer brought about by FDI. Developing nations now view investment as one of the most crucial ways to learn, upgrade their domestic industrial base, and improve the environment, even though many cutting-edge innovations aren't released onto the market. Without looking at project-level case studies, it is challenging to quantify the advantages of technology transfer. It is commonly recognized that short-term and long-term effects vary and that social and private gains might differ.

An evaluation of Bangladesh's competitive environment done in 2003 by CPD for the World Economic Forum (WEF) found that a consistent and large majority of respondents (86.5 percent) think that technology in the nation lags behind that in most other nations. In Bangladesh, FDI is cited by a growing percentage of respondents as a significant and potential source of new technology. However, they also admitted that the amount of technological transfer attributable to FDI had actually been quite small. This is largely due to the fact that, as was already said, the bulk of FDI creates low-quality jobs, notably in the EPZs, and that it is frequently not incorporated into a substantial network of domestic suppliers. Rare instances of technology and/or know-how transfer may take place in the banking industry, pharmaceutical industry, textile industry, agro-based sectors, and construction industry. Reverse engineering and labor mobility are crucial techniques of transferring technology and skills in some circumstances, it should be added.

Market Intelligence: Over the past ten years, there has been some shift in the general agreement regarding the relationships between FDI and foreign trade. Most crucially, TNC allocation choices, imports, and exports are all crucial components of an increasingly global system of production for goods and services. The notion that TNCs increasingly rely on trade in raw

materials and input goods within sister enterprises to maximize profit through transfer pricing is illustrated by the considerably larger shares of industrial input items that are imported by the foreign companies. For instance, the South Korean investors who arrived in Bangladesh in the late 1980s to make use of the textile quota provided by the Multi-Fiber Arrangement (MFA) brought with them a wealth of business knowledge. As a result, we see that over the past 20 years, local business owners have emulated South Koreans on an enormous scale by setting up production procedures and creating connections to international markets in order to advertise their goods. Other ways that the nation generates market intelligence include foreign investments in the manufacturing of cement, pharmaceuticals, and electricity. Local businesses in these industries have adopted the same strategies as foreign companies for acquiring machinery, gaining access to imported raw materials, and marketing textile products.

Rivalry: There is a complicated link between FDI and business sector competition. It is obvious that the arrival of foreign rivals into a market fosters competition, especially in those with lax enforcement of competition laws and market leaders that exert excessive influence over pricing. Competition from international investment boosts national efficiency as well, which raises the calibre of the produced goods. These efficiency advantages are produced by higher efficiency as well as improved labor and capital productivity. Improvements in product quality and price reductions of individual units are ultimately supported by these benefits. The aforementioned findings are supported by trends in the TNC-dominated toiletry and home chemicals market, which includes Lever Brothers.

However, as the TNCs steadily drive out numerous small and medium-sized local businesses from the market using a variety of market-capturing strategies, such as predatory pricing schemes, As a result of increased FDI flow and increased rivalry, local producers are primarily affected by displacement effects, which lead to a concentration of productive capacities in Bangladesh's economy. This relocation impact also suggests a shift in ownership.

Corporate Social Reasonability: In the current environment, it's critical to maximize shareholder value through corporate philanthropy. The extent to which businesses can concern about issues that go beyond their primary goal of generating profits is still up for debate. Although from the perspective of workers as mentioned in the CPD survey, there are only a few enterprises in Bangladesh that comply with health and safety requirements, some businesses may do it to safeguard their interests by providing regular health care for their personnel.

4.8 Relationship between Bangladesh's Economic Growth and FDI

Macro In terms of the economy, foreign direct investment has a lot of benefits, especially for Third World nations like Bangladesh where it helps to expand economic growth and production. FDI transfers money from sources abroad to countries that lack the resources to finance themselves domestically. Foreign investment helps to close the saving-investment gap since there aren't enough local savings to turn into investments (Ahmad 1990). Due to its high population density and low GDP per capita, Bangladesh in particular has difficult obstacles in expanding its cities (Sattar 1999). The influxes encourage the development of capital and the growth of numerous economic sectors, including manufacturing, infrastructure, and the energy industry. Increased work opportunities and a lower unemployment rate are both results of the expansion¹¹. GDP and per capita income increase as a result, which aids in the fight against poverty in emerging countries. Additionally, FDI strengthens linkages with developed countries, which leads to cost advantages through sophisticated technology transfers and advantageous externalities. An growth in financial links also leads to stronger capitalistic markets, corporate governance principles, and social responsibility ideas (supro.org). Bangladesh's trade policy has experienced significant liberalization as a result of the complex relationship between FDI and growth/development in order to maintain the inflows of money and investments from abroad. These aspects also support the government's efforts to promote the country as a suitable place for FDI, which has a number of benefits of its own. The results have confirmed an increased desire to instill in the populace knowledge and skills in order to raise national education spending and improve Bangladesh's labor force's competitiveness. To encourage FDI, however, it seems that local organizations like the Grameen Bank are more successful than FDI (through female empowerment).

The fall in local investment, economic development, and national saving rates in non-Asian nations has been attributed to foreign investment, claims Fry (1999). His research indicates that foreign direct investment (FDI) typically replaces and displaces domestic investments. However, foreign investment in South and East Asia has contributed to an increase in capital formation and has had similar good effects to domestic investment (Fry 1999). There isn't much domestic investment to drown out foreign investment, thus it can successfully promote economic growth and increase Bangladesh's GDP.

In a country like Bangladesh, where imports are the main source of income, the capital account deficit increases as foreign cash leaves the country. A crucial component of Bangladesh's long-term sustainable growth, according to Sattar (1999), is foreign direct investment (FDI). From this angle, FDI aids the growth of efficiency in a variety of economic sectors while also increasing GDP. The advantages of exports and FDI outflows are emphasized in this viewpoint by Sattar (1999). A government can produce foreign currency and enhance its capital account by allowing outflows; they may also help a surplus that already exists or, as in Bangladesh's case, lower a budget deficit and possibly pave the way for a surplus to arise in the future. Because there is a significant association between FDI inflows and higher imports, Fry claims that FDI inflows frequently hurt the capital account (1999). However, if such influxes help to boost production capacity, the economy may start to place more of an emphasis on exports and gain foreign currency (Fry 1999). Higher imports or foreign capital inflows made possible by the money earned will promote ongoing economic growth and development (Sattar 1999). In light of this, Bangladesh has adopted a growth strategy that is driven by the market and exports (www.supro.org). The current prosperity of the RMG sector is a good example of this cycle. Sattar emphasizes the reasoning for the regime of Bangladesh's trade policy (1999). FDI offers a lot of advantages, but capital flight is a constant worry. The country's current account and foreign exchange reserves would suffer as a result of this idea's implied domestic capital outflows. Foreign investment and international aid, according to Quazi (2004), frequently accelerate these outflows and impede economic growth. The paper claims that as entering foreign capital replaces local capital inside the borders of the host nation, FDI-generated foreign money assists in funding the exodus of domestic capital. However, a reduction in capital flight is listed as one benefit of FDI by Mondal (2003). This suggests that the benefits of FDI reduce the risk of home investments by stabilizing economic output and decreasing the desire to invest abroad.

GDP Growth Rate of Bangladesh; Source: Trading Economics

The relationship between FDI and economic growth hasn't been the subject of as many research. This has a number of justifications. In addition to foreign investment, a variety of other macroeconomic factors could also have an impact on growth and development; ignoring any of these factors raises concerns regarding biased empirical analysis as a result of omitted variables. This occurs when the statistical model is underspecified, which means that not all relevant factors have been taken into consideration, and a significant variable is omitted. Bias must exist for the deleted independent factors to have an effect on both the dependent variable and other independent variables in the equation. When independent variables are neglected, the effects of the independent variables that are taken into account in the regression are overemphasized. However, the downward bias overestimates the effects of the independent factors. The study may be gravely misinterpreted since independent variables commonly interact with one another and generate multicollinearity issues. Ahmad highlights the fact that there is a link between the factors (1990).

4.9 Dimensions of the barriers: Application of legislation & policy

The administrative hurdles' scope is highly complicated and intertwined in this situation. Administrative hurdles that deter potential FDI include poor policy design and implementation, competitive weakness, structural constraints, low quality infrastructure and skills, weak institutions, bad governance, and administrative burdens. The fundamental flaws in the bureaucratic system, however, are inefficiency and corruption, which make dealing with administrative workers a burdensome affair.

Additionally translated into various forms, administrative impediments differ from industry to industry. In Bangladesh, we are accustomed to encountering obstacles in the shape of several regulatory agencies' policies, laws, and functions. Two significant organizations that are directly involved in FDI operations are the National Board of Revenue (NBR) and the Board of Investment (the Investment Promotion Agency).

The price inefficiency is undoubtedly high: The majority of government bodies have inefficient, inept, and unresponsive governance and management. Inefficient services provided by state-owned companies in the banking, electricity, telecommunications, ports, and other public utilities have come at a great cost in terms of higher costs of doing business. Entrepreneurs have incurred significant costs as a result of power outages and voltage fluctuations, shortages of gas supply, particularly due to a limited network, limited telephone services, insufficient urban water supply, and the high incidental and transaction costs associated with these services. In reality, the public sector utility service providers' operations have been internally focused and have not performed well, and the justification for 'public' provision has often been lacking or non-existent. And a large portion of the performance gap they are seeing can be attributed to poor, inefficient management and unresponsive governance.

Corruption is a veiled taxing method: There may be a wide range of causes for the extent of government corruption. The more significant ones are organizational and economic policy-related in character, however many of them are cultural or sociological in nature. An atmosphere of widespread bureaucratic and regulatory constraints fosters corruption. Significant discretionary authority in the hands of the officials and a lax judicial system both contribute to corruption. Even though corruption affects several facets of society in various ways, the business community, investors, and entrepreneurs bear a disproportionate share of its expenses. For them, taxing in disguise is what corruption is. Businessmen are forced to bribe officials to get around restrictions and regulations when there aren't viable legal or administrative channels for redress. Bribery is sometimes viewed by businesses as one of the costs of doing business, and these payments are often recorded as real business expenses.

Policy inconsistency: Under its liberalized Industrial Policy and export-focused, private sector-led economic strategy, Bangladesh offers ample investment prospects, and the corresponding policies look good on paper. However, there are a number of policy inconsistencies that are more than enough to deter FDI.

Disparate treatment: Although current statutes guarantee both domestic and foreign investors equal treatment, discriminatory practices nevertheless persist with relation to foreign investment. Some of the areas of unequal treatment include sanctioning criteria for specific kinds of foreign investment, limitations on capacity development, unique regulations for supplier's credit, and pay-as-you-earn programs.

BOI one-stop service: The Board of Investment (BOI) in Bangladesh has established a cell to offer all kinds of services and support to private investors, including FDI. Offering a one-stop shop to current and potential investors has yet to actually happen, though. The employees of various state-owned utility service providers who work for BOI one stop service are less qualified and equipped to deliver the services that are required.

Arbitrary regulatory body: There are several government organizations that serve as regulatory bodies for the relevant industries in order to enable investment and economic activity. Despite the fact that these regulatory organizations were supposed to have operational autonomy, in reality this has not been the case. This has impacted their capacity to act swiftly and effectively in order to meet the demands and requirements of business owners and investors. For instance, the politicization of administration and diminished autonomy of Public Finance Institutions (PFIs) as a result of the Ministry of Finance's supervisory responsibility over them rather than Bangladesh Bank (Central Bank). As a result, time-intensive and necessary PFI services become less effective.

Legal enigma: In the majority of South Asian nations, the legal system is quite onerous, and laws are frequently not carried out as intended. The outdated laws and rules do not support the FDI policy incentives. The majority of the time, the judicial dispensation process is too drawn out and might sometimes take more than ten years to render a decision. For investors in general and international investors in particular, this is disappointing.

Intellectual property rights protection (IPR): Bangladesh is not working swiftly enough to guarantee that its laws and regulations are compliant with the WTO Agreement on Trade Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights, it has been noted (TRIPS). Despite the fact that the nation has IPR protection laws in place, they are insufficient. It is generally recognized that there is a clear correlation between higher levels of FDI and IPR protection, thus governments in South Asian nations must act quickly to preserve IPR against the backdrop of diminishing FDI flow.

Lawsuits: Taxpayers frequently file lawsuits against the government, and in most cases, the government loses. However, because of the lengthy legal process, businessmen find these cases to be inconvenient.

Implementation issues: The main problem with administrative barriers is the misalignment of trade- and investment-related policies, as well as the lack of coordination in the execution process between multiple government departments. Investors experience difficulties as a result, and corporate expenses increase.

Tax authorities' discretionary power: Tax officers have reportedly used their discretionary authority to harass investors and businesspeople. Tax officials had a lot of discretion, which led to corruption among many of them. Even individuals who are eager to pay taxes occasionally find themselves unable to do so because dishonest tax authorities will often ask people for a "percentage" in exchange for lowering the assessed value.

Registrant difficulty: Entrepreneurs have complained that the registration process with the sponsoring agency is tedious and useless. The regulations defining the duty of the inspector in reference to registration with the "Inspectorate of Factories and Establishments" appear to provide the inspector a great deal of discretionary power and disadvantage industries.

Insufficient coordination between state agencies: Investor pain increases as a result of a major lack of coordination amongst the government's agencies that implement policy. This causes numerous difficulties during the implementation process, puts obstacles in the way of investors receiving the proper government incentives, and eventually deters international investors from moving forward.

Financial changes: Any fiscal adjustment made after the Finance Act was passed seriously disrupts any business plan and deters FDI in particular. In Bangladesh, Statutory Regulatory Orders are frequently used to amend policies (SROs).

Protracted customs clearance: A consignment must have about 25 signatures before customs will release it. Furthermore, even when the cargo is not chosen for physical inspection, it takes longer than the allotted time to release a consignment under the supervision of a licensed PSI business.

Infrastructure: Another factor that influences the level of foreign investment is the level of infrastructure development, which is related to administrative barriers. It is difficult to assert that South Asian countries have attained an infrastructure development level that will satisfy foreign

investors. Once more, ineffective administrative and bureaucratic processes failed to boost adequate infrastructure support.

Restricted access to telecommunications: Comparatively to the majority of the other developing nations in the region, Bangladesh's telecommunications sector lags well behind, and the sector's approach has been largely inward-looking. Due to outdated telephone exchanges, transmission links, and public monopolies in fixed lines, the economy has paid a heavy price in terms of limited access to telephone connections, non-competitive pricing, and poor service quality. The expense of conducting business has gone up as a result.

Power source: Among developing nations, Bangladesh has one of the lowest rates of electrification and power usage per person. In the power industry, system losses have frequently approached 40% of gross generation. Government involvement in the power industry has led to a scenario where duties are overlapping and unclear. In actuality, the economy continues to bear a heavy burden from an insufficient and inefficient electricity supply. The frequent, severe load-shedding, especially during peak hours, has interrupted industrial productivity and reduced the nation's competitiveness abroad.

Costly ports: The cost of ineffective cargo handling at the Port has been particularly high, which has a negative impact on the economy's external competitiveness. The port is home to a large number of labor unions, all of which are essential for handling cargo. The entire system comes to a halt if one of these associations decides to organize a strike.

There are, of course, unofficial, hidden fees associated with clearing freight, whether it is for import or export. The fact that the port is one of the most costly ports in the world (in terms of containers) is solely because of these "unofficial" payments, of which the relevant authorities are pleasantly unaware despite clearly reaping the benefits.

Another factor that lengthens the lead time for shipments is inefficiency and bureaucratic gridlock. Therefore, even if a foreign customer is interested in placing an order from Bangladesh, the business is forced to buy the products from somewhere else if it is extremely urgent. Not only do the business owners lose, but the government also forfeits the port's owed duties and taxes.

4.10 Strategic conditions to reduce the barriers

There are a lot of advantages that Bangladesh possesses that can draw in foreign investment from both established and developing nations. The success in finding skilled and unskilled labor at

relatively low costs, as well as the growing supply of both keeping a generally stable macroeconomic climate is one of the characteristics that makes the nation appealing to foreign investors. They are generally aware that Bangladesh has some of the lowest wage rates in Asia, that inflation is typically kept within manageable bounds, that the exchange rate is comparatively stable, that the customs regulations are favourable to investment without discriminating between foreign and domestic investors, and that attractive incentive programs are available for foreign investors.

To persuade potential foreign investors that their involvement in economic activities in the country is valued, Bangladesh has to implement effective promotion methods. They might take advantage of investment incentives that are competitive with those provided by other nations in the area and the developing world, as well as friendly regulations. The nation must also advance by enacting laws that are welcoming to investment, streamlining regulatory procedures, and eliminating ineffective bureaucratic practices.

Nearly all growing Asian economies, including Bangladesh, have gradually embraced more open policies for FDI during the previous few decades, and this trend is likely to continue in the near future. This study's overall finding is that Bangladesh gains net benefits from FDI. These advantages appear to be crucial for merging the national economy with the global economy as well as for the transfer of technology and skills.

The worldwide experience indicates that the advantages of FDI can be extremely uneven, ambiguous, or even harmful depending on the country circumstances. But given its current traits, Bangladesh is poised to gain from increased FDI inflows. In order to increase FDI flows to Bangladesh, it is crucial to create an environment that encourages investment. For this, it's crucial to consider a number of policy topics, such as:

Governmental efficiency and quality: The nation's administrative structure requires necessary overhaul. To significantly increase its effectiveness and production, the bureaucracy must be reorganized. On a priority basis, bureaucratic oversight and meddling in business and investment operations should be reduced.

Law and order situation improvement: By making the necessary changes to law enforcement and implementing additional measures, the law as well as order situation has to be improved. For the rule of law to be established, political conflict to be avoided, and corruption to be reduced, a social agreement is required.

Infrastructure and human resource development: Both the public and private sectors must contribute to infrastructure development. To achieve this, it is necessary to have the right rules in place so that the private sector offering infrastructure services with ease. Similar to this, both public and private colleges should step up and introduce courses and programs that result in graduates with the technical and managerial abilities necessary in contemporary industrial and other activities. In this regard, Bangladesh stands a high possibility of being able to take part in the wealth and growth that are sweeping the rest of Asia if the government and the private sector work together to undertake efficient economic reforms in a successful manner.

Port service improvement: Despite recent progress, the effectiveness of port services can still be raised with the right actions. Similar to this, by making improvements to the customs clearance procedures, physical improvements and labor management system changes.

Privatization and additional reforms: The state-owned enterprise privatization program needs to be improved to encourage both domestic and foreign investment. To guarantee better and more effective services, it may be necessary to privatize a number of financial institutions and some public utilities. The policies should promote private sector involvement in a number of important industries, including as manufacturing, agricultural processing, infrastructure, including transportation, telecommunication, power, and ports, and the creation of high value-added goods.

Modernization of business law: In light of current global business practices and needs, it is critical that Bangladesh update and modernize all laws pertaining to commerce and investment.

Establishing industrial parks: Building new industrial parks can aid in fostering an atmosphere that is conducive to international investment. The presence of ready infrastructure and a safe, conducive investment environment can serve as a potent motivator in luring foreign investors to participate in successful companies.

Creation of new EPZs: To provide facilities to investors with an eye toward exports, the government may develop a phased program for creating new EPZs. The establishment of new EPZs may also be fostered by the business sector.

Improving the country's reputation abroad: Positive changes in the economy, society, and future prospects of the nation should be effectively projected abroad, especially among potential investors. This includes highlighting the country's welcoming investment climate and the resources available to foreign investors. Such "image development" initiatives would be essential to remove the unfavourable perceptions that have long persisted and deterred investors from

investing. In addition to the aforementioned, maintaining consistency in rules and behaviours is crucial to prevent investors from receiving the "wrong signal."

Policies relating to macroeconomic stability: The government should promote growth-promoting and growth-accommodating policies, take more steps to alleviate poverty more quickly, and adopt suitable policies to ensure macroeconomic stability in a sustainable way. Bangladesh has already made significant progress in this area, and in order to foster a favourable perception of the nation among potential foreign investors, accomplishments in both economic and social growth should be actively promoted overseas.

Economic and commercial diplomacy: In the current world, which is characterized by fast globalization and rising competitiveness, strengthening economic and commercial diplomacy is a crucial element in attracting FDI. Improved bilateral communication in this regard trigger for growing FDI inflows to Bangladesh may be Bangladesh's relations with potential investor nations. Additionally, it is critical to identify potential investors in other nations and take the necessary steps to entice them to invest in Bangladesh. This goes beyond simply strengthening ties with nations that have already done so.

4.11 Japanese FDI in Bangladesh

Since Bangladesh's independence in 1971, Japan has been the country with the single-largest investment. On February 10, 1972, Japan formally recognized Bangladesh as an independent nation following the conclusion of the liberation war. This day is significant since it marked the beginning of Bangladesh and Japan's bilateral cooperative relations. This year marks the 50th anniversary of this cordial friendship between the two nations. Japan provided Bangladesh with tremendous help during these years of friendship, aiding Bangladesh in creating its nation. Japan has launched a project with enormous potential to assist Bangladesh in developing its infrastructure, fostering regional collaboration, and becoming an economic success. In this position, Japan helps to act as catalysts, facilitators, role models, and ambassadors in Bangladesh, who will be the ones to bring about change in the country's socioeconomic situation. Japan's contribution as a field of study will reveal Japan's reflections, which may prove essential for Bangladesh's progress (Moni, 2006). Japan has invested in Bangladesh for about 50 years, however due to a number of governance-related issues, the Government of Bangladesh (GoB) is still unable to utilize foreign capital. Japan's assistance to the government through the development

project strategy, investment, policymaking, and support of commerce and business in the South Asian region can be very helpful (Youn, 2001). Additionally, Japan offers scholarships to Bangladeshi students so they can visit, study in, and spread the culture of Japan in Bangladesh. Japan has consistently supported Bangladesh since their diplomatic ties were established on February 10, 1972. Bangladesh was completely shattered as a result of the war; as a result, Japan continued to strengthen Bangladesh's spine. Japan has consistently provided Bangladesh with financial, technological, and other help. Bangladesh has received investments from Japan for both economic and infrastructure development. According to one respondent, "These ODAs have a lot to contribute to the overall socio-economic development of Bangladesh, which needs to be explored." Japanologists can help determine whether aid can be more successful in certain industries. Bangladesh will receive the second-highest ODA from Japan in South Asia, after India, by the year 2022. Many nations make investments in Bangladesh. However, Japan is considered the most significant development partner, as mentioned by the respondent.

Figure 10: Japanese Companies in Bangladesh (2005-2020); Source: JETRO (2021)

The fiscal year's budget for Bangladesh was unveiled in June 2021. Japan regularly provides funding to Bangladesh's government to support the budget. Bangladesh is a developing nation, and without Japan's assistance, it is unable to balance the budget at this time. Bangladesh's economic development requires international support, especially Japanese aid, in order to comprehend real-world experiences. More study of this paradigm is required in the field of

Japanese studies. Bangladesh receives assistance from Japan in the form of financial aid and knowledge exchange to help the country grow economically and meet the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). By 2041, Bangladesh's government plans to graduate from the Least Developed Countries (LDCs) and enter the developed world through inclusive development, thanks in large part to the creative use of Japanese support. Japan's contribution will be the catalyst for change in the growth of Bangladesh. The country representative for JETRO and president of JBCCI, Mr. Yuji Ando, recently stated: ***“The day when the number of Japanese enterprises to double will arrive in the near future if business environment is dramatically enhanced in addition to basic infrastructure.”*** (The Daily Star, 25 July 2021).

One of the largest donors to the UN Peacekeeping Operation is Japan (UNPKO). Japan has contributed significantly to preserving world peace and stability. Japan is investing in Bangladesh and has a good chance of profiting from Bangladesh's commerce and business, therefore it is also helping Bangladesh maintain peace and tranquillity. But let's say that Bangladesh's peace and stability are threatened. If that happens, it will stop developing, Japanese commerce and business will be severely disrupted, and they may suffer a significant loss. Japan has helped Bangladesh set up the Dhaka-based Peace Building Centre.

Bangladesh is a small country with a sizable population. Bangladesh may face difficulties if people continue to be unemployed or unskilled in order to support economic development; Japan is primarily concerned with Bangladesh's human capital development. Because of the enormous population in the productive land and the potential for significant trade and business, Japan places a high priority on it. According to sources, Bangladesh will receive USD 4.21 million from the Japanese government as part of the "The Human Resource Development Scholarship (JDS)" programme, which will be put into action in 2021. Additionally, Japan contributed USD 23 million to the "The Governance and Management Research and Training Facility Improvement Project," another project. Once more, experts emphasize the importance of collaboration between business and academics to meet market demand and usher in the fourth industrial revolution (4IR). Additionally, Japan's participation might strengthen ties between business and academia for fair employment opportunities and preserve human resources for inclusive growth in the region.

Japan is currently concentrating on the South Asian continent for its potential future market. YKK is the most well-known Japanese investor working at the Dhaka EPZ, and Bangladesh today has more than 21 Japanese companies operating inside export processing zones (EPZs) and 40 outside

EPZs. Japan will find South Asia to be a lucrative export and import market, including for raw materials. Bangladesh's excellent location close to the Bay of Bengal allows for easy marine travel between Japan and other South Asian nations. Japan aids Bangladesh in expanding its seaports so that it might become a centre for trade among Asian nations. The contribution from Japan presents numerous chances to play important roles in how Japan's trade with Bangladesh and South Asia develops in the future. To create Bangladesh's first deep seaport at Matarbari, Cox's Bazar, Japan is making investments there. Bangladesh is now one of the most economically, industrially, and commercially valuable countries in this region thanks to Japan's sponsorship of the BIG-B.

Japan wants to develop its ideas about the rule of law, freedom of navigation, and an open market economy through constructive engagement with Bangladesh. It emphasized how the Free and Open Indo-Pacific (FOIP) would contribute to Bangladesh's long-term development. To advance the objective of regional peace, stability, and development set forth by FOIP, Japan is encouraging practical cooperation with Bangladesh. The BIG-B initiative, funded by Japan, aims to help Bangladesh establish itself as a dominant economic force in the Indo-Pacific region. Bangladesh will greatly benefit from the FOIP in terms of future economic growth. Understanding Japan's contribution would help in evaluating Bangladesh and its regional geopolitics objectively in order to promote peace, security, and stability. According to Mr. Zakir Ibne Hai, Corporate Affairs and Communications Director of JTI Bangladesh, ***"Since the purchase in December 2018, we gave BDT 8,500 crores (USD 1.0 billion) to NBR in various forms, making us the second-largest revenue provider to the national exchequer"*** (The Asahi Shimbun, 16 July 2019).

4.12 Comprehensive development of Bangladesh & Japan's contribution

Japan's assistance to Bangladesh is essential for fostering closer ties between the two countries and reaping the benefits of extensive cooperation as the country's top development partner. Japan helps Bangladesh in a variety of ways, including economic expansion, the development of human capital, technological innovation, and the mitigation of disaster risk. Japan has pledged to quicken Bangladesh's progress toward achieving the SDGs ever since their first diplomatic exchanges. Japan suggested working with Bangladesh to expand the southern Chattogram region, concentrating on the Matarbari projects that are now being built. According to the Japan International Cooperation Agency, Japan's The Bay of Bengal Industrial Growth Belt (Big-B) project plan can link the entire region and deepen ties (JICA, 2014). Some see Japan as Bangladesh's reliable and consistent development partner, particularly in reaching the SDGs

Table 1. Contemporary projects of Japan in Bangladesh for development

Projects Name	Budget (In Million USD)
Chattogram—Cox's Bazar Highway Improvement Project (E/S)	16.6
Dhaka Mass Rapid Transit Development Project (IV)	630.3
Dhaka Mass Rapid Transit Development Project (Line 5 Northern Route) (I)	486.1
Food Value Chain Improvement Project	97.9
Hazrat Shahjalal International Airport Expansion Project (II)	697.9
Jamuna Railway Bridge Construction Project (II)	776.2
Matarbari Port Development Project	206.7
Mirsarai Economic Zone	59.2
Urban Development and City Governance Project	246.2

Source: Embassy of Japan in Bangladesh, (n.d).

(Centre for Policy Dialogue, 2019). Japan has historically provided Bangladesh with a range of technological support, which has been extremely helpful to Bangladesh's overall growth. By emulating Japan's technological advancement, Japanologists could make a significant contribution to Bangladesh's technological advancement. Trade and business with Japan and among the regions will prosper if all of its successful policies are properly put into practice. As shown in Table 1, Bangladesh will greatly benefit from technical help from Japan to achieve inclusive development. Since 1978, Japan has been the leading official development assistance (ODA) donor in Asia. Japan is the greatest ODA donor in the world, contributing nearly two-thirds of its \$10 billion annual ODA commitment to Asia. With active initiatives totalling USD 1.7 billion in Matarbari Coal and Port projects, Mass Rapid Transit (MRT) routes, and the prevention of non-

communicable diseases, Japan is the largest and most reliable foreign aid partner. The process of achieving SDGs will take on new dimensions as a result of these significant projects. This fiscal year, Japan has overtaken the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank as Bangladesh's top lender in terms of aid disbursement. The largest bilateral donor to the country donated USD 714.44 million in aid in 2020–21, more than twice the amount granted by the World Bank and Asian Development Bank combined, according to officials of the Economic Relations Division (ERD). During the same time frame, the World Bank released USD 414 million, while the Asian Development Bank released USD 300 million (Kabir, 2021). Bangladesh received USD 1.69 billion from Japan's development partner, the JICA, in FY2020. Japan provided Bangladesh with USD 14.25 billion in aid between FY2010 and FY2020. Japan supports Bangladesh's efforts to create a "just, democratic, and prosperous" society that is less dependent on outside aid.

Bangladesh is home to a number of vital and high-priority projects that the JICA is funding, such as the third terminal at Shahjalal International Airport in the city, the Dhaka Metrorail system, and a rail bridge across the enormous Jamuna River. Additionally, Japan is helping Bangladesh build and expand a number of economic zones under various names, including Special Economic Zones (SEZ) and Exclusive Economic Zones (EEZ). In the years to come, Bangladesh's socioeconomic development may have helped the country make economic strides toward achieving the SDGs. In the meantime, JICA has consented to sign the largest-ever Official Development Assistance (ODA) agreement in the history of the world, worth USD 3.2 billion, to finance seven government-run projects in Bangladesh. The agreement has a 30-year maturity and a 0.65% interest rate. Additionally, Bangladesh has been given a ten-year grace period on previously borrowed debts. The amount distribution pattern is balanced and meets the needs of each type. With their in-depth knowledge of Japanese values, norms, customs, and culture, Japanologists from Bangladesh can play a key role in promoting the Japanese government's decision to increase ODA. Japanologists are well-equipped to act as a facilitator in maximizing the impact of ODA.

However, the existing literature does not sufficiently cover a proper understanding of the reasons behind the sectors in which Japan is investing in Bangladesh. Also, it is not clear how this cooperation is helping the progress of Bangladesh. There is even little understanding as to why Japan was so supportive of Bangladesh economically. This paper will be able to give a clear idea about these issues.

FDI has grown to be a key part of international trade for many nations. Asian nations today have a significant impact on the global economy, but south Asian nations of which Bangladesh is the leader are significantly falling behind. This paper's general goal is to identify the factors that influence, hinder, provide a favourable environment for, and have the potential for, FDI in Bangladesh. This paper will also insight a deep look on what extent foreign investors, particularly Japanese investors, are increasingly investing in infrastructure projects related to energy, petroleum, air travel, and maritime communication. Besides these, the specific objectives of this paper are-

- To analysis how and to what extent Japanese investment is playing a role in the progress of Bangladesh.
- Understanding how Japanese investment is able to keep Bangladesh competitive internationally.
- To find the future areas of Japanese investment in Bangladesh.

To support the objectives this study responds to the subsequent research question:

What is the future of Japanese Foreign Direct Investment in Bangladesh particularly related to the Special Economic Zone located in Araihasar, Narayanganj?

5. METHODOLOGY

This discussion mainly prosecutes through the field visit on Araihasar, Narayanganj. Because it intends to ascertain both the facts that are already known about the phenomenon and those that have not yet been studied, the study will take an exploratory approach to the topic. Exploratory research will give the study the ability to examine the issue from both a descriptive and exploratory perspective. The researcher will use secondary sources to gather data for this study. The secondary sources will include WTO reports, reports from the RBI, reports on global investments, reports from the World Bank, publications from the Bangladesh government's ministry of commerce various financial websites such as, JETRO, BEPZA etc. and various newspapers.

6. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

This paper has been written with respect to travel to only one economic zone which may be somewhat inaccurate in giving an idea of total Foreign Direct Investment idea in Bangladesh. Also, since its data is analysed from one's own perspective, it may be somewhat biased.

7. DISCUSSION

7.1 Description about Field Visit

7.1.1 Starting the journey

December 29, 2022, we, the 4th batch students of the Japanese Studies Department, went to Bangladesh Special Economic Zone (BSEZ) located at Arai Hazar in Narayanganj as part of a field visit. We started our journey at 9.00 am. Our team of 42 people was led by our course teacher Abdullah Al Mamun sir. Also Khaled Mohammad Faisal, Secretary of DUJSAA was with us throughout.

7.1.2 On the way

It took us around 1.30 hours to reach the destination. While going, the names of several industrial companies could be seen through the gap in the glass of the cart. Eg- Meril, Brothers Group, KSRM Warehouse, ASBRM Steel Limited, PSRM, Gazi Pipes, Partex Tissue Limited, SF Textile Industries Limited, Bangla Cat, Nitol Motors Limited, Hi-Tech Steel and Rolling Mills Limited, Desh Tanks Limited, New Zealand Dairy, Seven Rings Cement, V-Nitewear and Composite Limited etc. As far as I understood, the Narayanganj area can be called the center of the big industries of Bangladesh.

7.1.3 At Destination

We were first impressed upon entering the destination. The whole way from the gate to the office was so clean and tidy that it was hard to believe that it was a place in Bangladesh. Anyway, I would like to divide our whole trip into two parts. The first part was the presentation and the second part was the site visit.

BSEZ ; Source: Araihaazar Economic Zone

Part 1: Presentation

As we entered the room we were taken to for the presentation, there was a hallway. Some people were working quite orderly. They welcomed us in Japanese. Then we were taken to the presentation room. The presentation was divided into three parts. These are-

1. Giving an idea about Sumitomo company
2. Brief description about Industrial Park
3. To give an idea of what is BSEZ, why and progress of its work

The first two parts were described by Sumitomo Corporation Managing Director Mr. Kouachi San. The last part was described by Umme San, office manager of Sumitomo Corporation.

7.1.3.1 What is Sumitomo?

The business of trading services is one that Sumitomo Corp. engages in. It works through the following divisions: Mineral Resources, Energy, Chemical & Electronics; Transportation &

Construction Systems; Infrastructure; Media & Digital; Living Related & Real Estate; and Metal Products. The trade of non-ferrous metals like titanium and aluminum, as well as steel sheets, tubular goods, and other products, is handled by the Metal Products segment. The businesses related to cars, ships, planes, trains, other forms of transportation equipment, and construction equipment are included in the Transportation & Construction Systems segment. The enterprises involved in social infrastructure, international power infrastructure, and logistical infrastructure are all part of the infrastructure industry. The companies related to digital, media, and smart communications platforms are handled by the Media & Digital sector. The food and agricultural, materials and supplies, lifestyle and retail, and real estate companies are all managed by the sector titled "Living Related & Real Estate." The segment of Mineral Resources, Energy, Chemical & Electronics creates firms in the fields of life sciences, basic chemicals, and electronics. The business was established on December 24, 1919, and has its corporate headquarters in Tokyo, Japan.

7.1.3.2 What is Industrial Park?

Definition

An area of the city set aside expressly for industrial use is called an industrial park. Commercial or residential usage is not permitted in these zones. Ports, refineries, warehouses, factories, distribution centers, and industrial parks are common.

The majority of industrial parks are located where the environment is suitable for such activity. Additionally, businesses who have their headquarters in the designated industrial park are eligible for tax breaks. Transport, storage, and production may all be combined in one place as a result of industrial parks. Chemical companies, steel mills, food and beverage processors, plastics producers, and airports may all be affected by this.

An industrial park, for instance, that is close to a significant port will have access to a railroad and a number of roads that serve as important channels for the movement of trucks and other large, heavy vehicles that transport goods. This industrial park will accommodate a variety of firms, such as cold storage facilities, engine part manufacturers, and distribution warehouses.

Importance

1. The Best Long-Term Investment of Locators

Business owners and even start-up establishments have begun to see that industrial parks represent the most excellent environment for entrepreneurs. Here we take a look at the characteristics of

industrial parks to assist you in seeing a clearer perspective. How it can serve a locator's growth and advancement over time and how it can highly contribute to a business's development? Here are the following reasons:

- Its sole purpose is to be complementary to production and manufacturing.
- Purposed for production for small and medium manufacturers.
- Built in a special economic zone that contains mutually beneficial businesses and industries.
- Subsidized service and infrastructure such as roads, electricity, energy, water supply, gas supply, and telecommunication services, among others.

Due to the cost implications for machinery and components, locators investing in industrial parks can rapidly reduce their manufacturing expenses. As a result, duty payments and delivery are more practical and effective. These all have the potential to be huge advantages in promoting export activities and increasing production to meet consumer demand. These will undoubtedly have a significant impact on business.

2. Outstanding Eye For Foreign Investors

International relations have grown as a result of industrial parks' increasing value. Every nation already has a certain market niche and competitive advantage that it offers to foreign and international investors. For instance, the Philippines is a nation with a developing economy that makes sense for foreign investors to assist. The nation is regarded as one of the fastest-growing nations, and it has a sizable amount of natural resources, highly trainable labor, and rising infrastructure. Investors are currently interested in a number of potential locations, including industrial parks in the Philippines.

The best places for enterprises to start off are typically industrial parks. This is a result of their extensive and modern infrastructures, which are paired with the most advantageous features for a nation.

3. Benefits to the Environment

Manufacturing firms are doing a fantastic job of looking for ways to reduce the environmental effects of their products' manufacture, from pre- through post-production. Industrial parks have developed to build a completely new field of sustainability because they are large-scaled locations. These refer to ideas of infrastructure, energy, waste, and environmental design that are intended

to be more ecologically conscious. The following are some advantages for the environment that industrial parks can offer:

- A reduction in air emissions
- Contaminated surface waters and depleted groundwater
- Conserving water
- Reduced emissions of greenhouse gases
- Recycled materials and resource conservation
- Reliable and accessible electricity, energy, and technology

It is clear how these elements, when combined, could have an effect on environmental standards. Industrial parks embrace sustainability and are conscious of its implications on the environment and society. Because of this, they were able to design a system that allows for the quicker manufacture of goods while causing the least amount of waste and environmental damage possible.

4. Improvement For Profits And Competitive Positions

One receiver advantage for the environment, the economy, and the community when one chose to locate in an industrial park. When these factors are improved and raised, a company's market reputation quickly rises to the top. In terms of the neighborhood, industrial parks provide employment, strengthen the tax base, encourage business retention, and lower development costs. On the other hand, it can offer the economy a wide range of advantages. Locators have access to funding, a better market and company reputation, more profitability, and many other benefits. If one wants to build an industrial park, first of all one needs agricultural land. Then to raise that place, infrastructure development, then finally, one can build their industry.

7.1.3.3 What is BSEZ?

Developing a special economic zone (Note 1; henceforth, "SEZ") in the Narayanganj District of the Dhaka Division of Bangladesh has been agreed upon by Sumitomo Corporation (Head Office: Chiyoda-ku, Tokyo; Representative Director, President, and Chief Executive Officer: Masayuki Hyodo). The joint venture agreement between the two parties was completed, and this summer the SEZ's development business, tentatively called Bangladesh SEZ Ltd., will be established.

Poster of the grand opening; Source: Araihaazar Economic Zone

Bangladesh is strategically located between South Asia and Southeast Asia, bordering India to the north, east, and west, as well as Myanmar to the southeast. One of the most populous nations in the world, India has 160 million residents (1.3 times as many as Japan), who live on terrain that is only around 40% the size of Japan. With a work force that is expected to grow by more than 2 million people year over the next 20 years or more, it boasts a plethora of human resources. Expectations for Bangladesh as a consumer market are high given that the country's population is predicted to continue growing until roughly 2055, and there has been an increase in recent years in the number of foreign businesses setting up shop there. To lay the groundwork for industrial diversification, Bangladeshi government is looking to develop 100 special economic zones nationwide over a period of 15 years, and even more companies are expected to set up operations there in future. ²

The SEZ is around 32 kilometers (about one hour's drive) east of the city center of Dhaka. An industrial park that would eventually be expanded across 190 hectares will be built out first. Operations are expected to start in fiscal 2021, with sales starting in 2020 at the same time as the

surrounding infrastructure development construction work. In the development business, Sumitomo Corporation will own a 76% interest. Over 13 billion yen in expenses for the project are anticipated. By way of an official development assistance project, the Japan International Cooperation Agency intends to develop this SEZ (JICA). The Bangladeshi government receives a yen loan from JICA to pay for construction projects related to the development of the local infrastructure.

In Indonesia, the Philippines, Vietnam, Myanmar, and India, Sumitomo Corporation is constructing, selling, and managing industrial parks and special economic zones. Sumitomo Corporation has invested in 7 industrial parks as of May 2019, and they are home to 519 tenant businesses with up to 210,000 employees. Sumitomo Corporation will support tenant businesses operating in this new SEZ in Bangladesh by providing support in completing administrative procedures for registering and applying for permits locally and by using the operational know-how gained through the implementation of earlier projects. By developing this SEZ, Sumitomo Corporation will contribute to industrial development and diversification as well as job creation in Bangladesh.

Historical event

The Late Prime Minister of Japan, Shinzo Abe visited Bangladesh on September, 2014. Then, The Development of Economic Zone was mentioned in joint statement between Bangladesh and Japan. In 2019, the incorporation of BSEZ was held. Sumitomo corporation (76%) and BEZA (24%) agreed to establish JV. Land filling work was started from August, 2020 supported by JICA. The land filling work was done by TOA Corporation. Infrastructure construction was started in December, 2021 by JGC. The construction work was finished at the end of November, 2022. Finally, BSEZ had inauguration ceremony on 6th December, 2022 at Araihasar. HPM also attended this ceremony.

Total Development Area

The total development area of the BSEZ is 190ha which is divided into 2 phase.

Phase 1: 83ha / 200acre

Phase 2: 107ha / 265acre

Besides these, there is also expansion area which is 100-200ha.

Motto of BSEZ: To ensure and maintain Japan Quality in Bangladesh

Japan Quality in Bangladesh		BSEZ	
EZ Operation			
Construction	DANUBA BUILDERS & ENGINEERING LTD		
Security			
Telecom/DX	bradNet		

The co-operative company of Bangladesh and Japan; Source: Araihaazar Economic Zone

Sales Updates

The work of Phase 1 is already completed. Here, only "Singer" has already started the establishment of their company. Construction materials, chemicals and daily goods companies are under discussion. Over 10ha area is reserved for large plot. Nicca, ONODA and Rudolf has already reserved their plot. EZ Office Warehouse and WPP, STP is considered for the future plan. Thirty Japanese companies and 10 other foreign companies have shown their interest to invest in the zone.

The work of phase 2 is about to start. Here, the construction of the rental factory, gas station and sub-station are running.

Government procedure is one of the main barriers to work in Bangladesh. This process is so lengthy and time-consuming. Besides, Bangladesh is underdeveloped compared to Singapore or others. For this reason, it is becoming hard for Japan to continue their work. But, they are hopeful that they will be able to overcome these difficulties.

2. *What type of companies can be built in industrial park? ¹*

Since Bangladesh is already developed in the garment sector, there are very few plans for this sector. Basically, chemical, automobile sectors are being prioritized here.

3. *How can Bangladesh address the economic effects of LDC graduation after 2026 with aid from the BSEZ? ²*

Industry diversification, employment creation, the transfer of new technology, and the expansion of import-export trade would all benefit from the FDI inflows. These will aid in accelerating the nation's economic growth.

Discussion about the field visit; Source: Araihaazar Economic Zone

4. *How do you persuade investors in this place to respond? How many Japanese businesses are planning to invest in the area?*¹

From FDI, we have received a direct query. I'm not sure how much money Japanese businesses have invested, but as I have indicated, we've already begun talks with 30 of them.

5. *What is the future plan about BSEZ?*¹

First, we'll make an effort to draw FDI to our economic zone. Second, we'll offer services and infrastructure that meet international standards. Thirdly, we'll offer platform services to nearby skilled people in an effort to raise their level of living.

6. *Why you choose Bangladesh?*²

Because, the market is very large in Bangladesh. As well as, the labor cost is so poor and a large-scale labor is available here.

7. *Why did you choose Araihasar except any other areas like Chittagong?*²

As Dhaka is the main city and the distance is less from Dhaka, we choose this area. Even, international facilities are available here. So, it's the best for establishing SEZ.

8. *After 10 years, what will be your expectations about this area?*²

Japanese companies don't come to do business for 10 or 20 years. They come for 200 to 250 years. So, here is same.

Part 2: Site Visit

Then the second part of our journey began with Site Visit.

Waste Water Pumping Machine: Through this, the processing of waste will be done first. This will work in terms of ECR-1987 law. Then, it will be discharge after making these waste safe for the environment.⁵

Waste water pumping machine; Source: Araihaazar Economic Zone

Fire Executors: It is designed to extinguish fire in emergency situations. This is well organised and all planned. It will work immediately in time of emergency. ⁴

Fire executors; Source: Araihaazar Economic Zone

Green Zone: Every investors will have to keep a green zone in their business area. This is a mandatory law to establish business hub here. ⁴

Carbon Emission Plan: According to BEZA and ECR plan, there will be a range for every company to release and control carbon. They will have to be obliged it. Even, the Japanese process of "Carbon absorbing" may be accepted after it will be examined by Bangladesh.

Internet Server: This is controlled by now BTCL. After the establishment of our own server area, we can manage this sector ourselves. ⁴

Transformer Station: To control electricity and power generator, a 33kb voltage transformer station is established. But, the voltage needs to be higher. So, a 230kb voltage transformer station was proposed to build up but this was disagreed by the government as the government wants to control this area by their management system. If it doesn't approve in future also, the Polli Bidyut Station at Volta district will then support this sector. ⁵

Transformer station; Source: Araihaazar Economic Zone

Road System: The main road will be one way. This road will not be used for products load and unload process. For custom hessels, there will be own bay for every company in front of the main road. ¹

One way road system; Source: Araihasar Economic Zone

The Construction of Singer: Singer is building their company on A6, A7 and A8 area of Phase 1. They will start their production next year that is hoped to 800crore. ⁵

That's all about our site visit. We only visited the phase 1 as the work of this part completed.

About 180 million USD has cost for this phase. Yet, the work of manufacturing sector is left. Only the the work of construction sector is done. Even, they are now selling only the plot of phase 1, the others are still not sold as those are not prepared. Lastly, it is hoped that about 1 lakh employment will be ensured after the construction of this BSEZ and this enlightens the bright future of our country. ⁵

7.1.4 Back to home

Then we have lunch together. At 3.30 we saw everyone off and boarded the bus and reached the university by 4.30. By that time, standing in front of a gray desert, the bright economic prosperity of Bangladesh is floating in our eyes.

7.2 Findings of the Field Trip

7.2.1 The Perspective Plan of Bangladesh

In an effort to move the country toward progress, the Bangladeshi government has approved Vision 2041 as a continuation of Digital Bangladesh Vision 2021. In particular, Vision 2041 aims to end severe poverty by 2031, achieve Upper Middle-Income Country (UMIC) status, and reach High-Income Country (HIC) status by 2041, with poverty all but eradicated (Arrow,2002). This publication introduces "Making Vision 2041 a Reality: Perspective Plan of Bangladesh 2021-2041," a development strategy comprising policies and programs (PP2041). Four institutional pillars—the people, who are the primary forces behind development and transformation—are the foundation of Vision 2041 and the related PP2041 plan (Scheffer, 2019). The first four are governance, second is democratization, third is decentralization, and fourth is capacity building. The benefits of rapid expansion will be distributed fairly to all people, with a focus on the weak and the poor, in order to strike a balance. In this regard, food security is one of the crucial factors mentioned in the paper. The text strives to create an agriculture that is long-term resilient to climate change, diverse, and ensures food security and nutrition (Enam, 2007). The text also emphasizes the significance of taking action to prevent food waste, particularly post-harvest loss and chronic waste of expensive goods by the wealthy.

The Policy makes a number of adjustments to agriculture in an effort to bridge the transition from rural agrarian economies to industrial and digital economies and ensuring that everyone has access to education and food security (Asiedu, 2010). The following are some of the agricultural sector's future priorities as outlined in the policy: fostering opportunities for Sustainable Agriculture and Green Precision Agriculture; focusing on soil and water conservation; land development; drainage and flood control; and reclamation programs; encouraging agricultural diversification and the expansion of horticultural crops; introducing and popularizing Good Agricultural Practices (GAP); farm mechanization; and post-harvest management in order (Borensztein, 2020).

The approach to transition to a high-income Economy will depend heavily on the urban shift. The goal of Vision 2041 is for all citizens to be guaranteed a minimum standard of living by the year 2041, based on employment income for everyone looking for work and social protection benefits for the most vulnerable citizens who are unable to participate in the labor market due to old age and physical disabilities (Keller, 2016). In the document, significant elements for reducing poverty are analyzed based on prior experiences. Improvements in farm productivity and incomes, the growth of rural non-farm employment due to remittance inflows, infrastructure improvements in rural areas, microcredit programs, the expansion of low-skilled manufacturing jobs, particularly in the garment industry, and the expansion of urban service activities are all factors that have been particularly helpful for reducing poverty. The development of microcredits, according to the text, is crucial for generating non-farm employment, enhancing the poor's asset base, and regulating consumption. Furthering the reduction of extreme poverty will require continued attention to microcredit (Naren, 2005). The text states that agriculture will continue to be a significant factor in reducing poverty, particularly during the interim period between now and FY2031.

On the other hand, Vision 2041's fourth pillar is capacity building. To adapt institutions to a changing economy that is centered on strategic relationships, resource development, and internal management and operations, institutions must be strengthened in their capabilities. The finance will be expanded upon in the PP2041 plan (Lipsey, 2009). The goal would be to improve the poor's overall access to institutional credit, lower credit costs, and increase the poor's access to microcredit in general. Credit bureaus, credit guarantee programs, and a variety of FinTech initiatives are just a few of the steps that will be used to strengthen the credit market. The manifesto takes a gender-based perspective and a "leaving no one behind" stance (Taylor, 2017). The importance of women participating in technical education, skill development, and rural training is

emphasized. The PP2041 will focus on expanding and updating the current TVET Institutes with rural technology to meet the challenge of the rapidly evolving rural economy.

Perspective plan of Bangladesh; Source: The Business Standard

Last but not least, the Policy aims to create a Bangladesh that is resistant to climate change and other environmental problems. In most of the poor districts, the study notes a high sensitivity to natural disasters due to flooding, river erosion, sea level rise, and other natural catastrophes, highlighting the connection between poverty and vulnerability to natural disasters and climate change (Morgan.,1998). The Bangladesh Delta Plan 2100 (BDP2100), a significant long-term project sponsored by the government, aims to enhance management of water, land, ecology, environment, and climate change through strategies, policies, investment programs, and institutions (Yasuda, 2011). The BDP2100 aims to specifically address the vulnerabilities of Bangladesh brought on by geography and climate change by tackling these risks at their very source. During PP2041, the linked strategies for flood control, water storage, irrigation, land management, agriculture, forestry resource management, and ecological balance will make up a significant portion of the policy package for decreasing poverty and enhancing environmental

management (Miller, 2006). The policy also contains specific measures to improve the adaptability of agricultural production systems, particularly: proper soil and nutrient management; better water harvesting and retention; and conservation agriculture with minimal tillage and residue retention.

7.2.2 Impact of FDI on achieving the Perspective Plan

Growing internationalization and global economic integration, as seen by an increase in international commerce and foreign direct investment, have been two of the most notable trends in the world economy over the past 20 years (FDI). It has long been a contentious issue to discuss the role of foreign direct investment (FDI) in the growth process. There is surprisingly little analysis of the topic, despite the fact that this discussion has offered insightful information about the connections between FDI and growth. Economic growth in emerging countries is typically influenced favorably by FD (Srivastava, 2003). A capital-poor nation like Bangladesh can use it to increase physical capital, create employment opportunities, develop productive capacity, improve the skills of local laborers through the transfer of technology and managerial know-how, and aid in the integration of the national economy with the global economy (Macquere, 2018). There are insufficient mechanisms in Bangladesh's investment plans to support the growth of foreign investment over time. The reform measures haven't been very successful in fostering the environment that will encourage foreign direct investment because there isn't a long-term industrial development strategy in place (Lucas, 2012). The current state of FDI in Bangladesh is not yet satisfactory, but given the availability of plentiful resources, skilled and affordable labor forces, a stable political climate, effective monetary and fiscal policy, improvements to the infrastructure, and long-term strategic planning to stimulate FDI, it may be possible to create the conditions necessary to draw FDI to Bangladesh.

7.2.3 Contribution of FDI on the GDP of Bangladesh

The World Bank estimates that Bangladesh's GDP will increase by more than six times in real terms from \$53.37 billion in 2000 to \$324.24 billion in 2020, demonstrating the country's remarkable economic growth over the past 20 years (Loore, 1999). This has been made possible by a structural change in the financial and trade markets that has tapped the combined power of cross-sector labor reallocation and capital deepening.

As nations shut down in order to stop the virus' spread, there was a significant decline in output that led to unheard-of reactions on the economic front. The financial markets in wealthy nations

were stabilized by massive central bank intervention, and strong government spending protected businesses and households from the harshest effects of the recession (Anderson, 2015). A fiscal expansionary policy carries a higher level of liquidity risk. With normal liquidity risk configurations in Bangladesh, economic development occurs in stages. While exports and remittances are frequently the only sources of foreign currency in non-investment grade nations like Bangladesh, access to international credit markets is difficult.

Bangladesh should anticipate a decrease in international commitments to ODA as a result of the imminent LDC graduation (Mac, 2007). The government of Bangladesh's recent decision to use \$313 million of its foreign currency reserves to fund capital projects is likely to erode the confidence of the international investor community and could pave the way for a reduction in the country's sovereign credit rating (Ishikawa, 2006).

To maintain its balance of payments, Bangladesh is actually incredibly reliant on international funding. Short-term debt inflows are probably going to be further restricted as a result of the regime change in the interest rate environment that has caused a downward shift in its yield curve posture (Kumar, 2013). Even if speculative capital inflows have the potential to destabilize the domestic financial and credit markets, continuous above-average risk-adjusted returns can guarantee ongoing portfolio flows into the capital markets (Herbert, 2016). According to this perspective, market restraint or exposure to liquidity risk will stop the country's policymakers from spending their way to a structurally viable path of debt sustainability.

If reducing liquidity risks is a goal of national policy, it can be achieved, for instance, through price and capital controls. However, coordination between fiscal and monetary policies will primarily give Bangladesh's government the necessary room to maneuver on policy issues in order to ensure sustainable growth and development (Baron, 2014). Having a banking division within the finance ministry definitely limits Bangladesh Bank's independence, yet it is not simple to achieve the necessary levels of policy coordination for a pro-development redesign of the country's financial system (Pitter, 2009).

Direct investors (i.e., FDI) and asset managers from advanced economies could help Bangladesh expand its external balance sheet by boosting their involvement in the local bond markets as well as in the country's foreign currency-denominated corporate bond markets (Nephier, 2006). Although government bonds predominate in Bangladesh's relatively underdeveloped secondary bond market, a greater reliance on domestically denominated public debt helps to mitigate the

currency mismatch in its balance sheet and creates duration mismatches as a result of the prohibitive costs of issuing long-term government securities and the lack of adequate governance of asset-liability immunisation risk (Xavier, 2003). Due to the limited access to non-deliverable futures or active swap markets, it also transfers currency risk to potential global lenders, increasing

susceptibility to speculative, non-resident investor behavior.

GDP growth and FDI in Bangladesh; Source: MDPI

A vicious cycle of currency depreciation, declining debt sustainability, and constrained fiscal space can result from strongly net negative, even fluctuating, portfolio flows to Bangladesh (Milton, 2015). This is because of Bangladesh's vulnerabilities. In order to support Bangladesh's structural transformation, long-term FDI is therefore a lower-risk strategy that causes decreases in sovereign credit spreads and increases the value of debt denominated in foreign currencies, which also affects the balance sheets and refinancing risks of private borrowers.

7.2.4 The Prospects of FDI in Bangladesh

Bangladesh has recently made progress in its economic development. By 2030, the country's GDP per capita is predicted to surpass India's, thanks to the nation's practically unparalleled growth rate, which is expected to increase to 7% in 2020. According to the World Bank, the percentage of people living in poverty has dramatically decreased from more than 40% in 1991 to about 14%

in 2016/17. Bangladesh, which is the world's most populous and economically significant LDC, aspires to leave the UN's LDC category in 2024.

The nation has been heralded by *The Economist* as the next Asian Tiger. And this may be seen in the investor interest. According to the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development, it saw its highest level of foreign direct investment (FDI) last year, totaling \$3.61 billion (Bidisha, 2005). This substantial increase highlights the domestic market's untapped potential and the lack of FDI Bangladesh has previously attracted.

Bangladesh is undergoing development changes akin to those India underwent in recent years, and we predict that it will soon become one of the region's most powerful economies. Since more than 10 years ago, we have been making investments in Bangladesh and are enthusiastic about the potential for economic progress there as well as the advantages it may provide for the local population (George, 2020). Our investments span a number of industries, including communications, manufacturing, and trade, although infrastructure makes up the majority of our portfolio's value (80%). Finance, home manufacturing, and infrastructure are three areas in which we have a particular interest.

With a population of slightly over 160 million, the nation has a high consumer demand, and the market for consumer products—which includes everything from white goods and clothing to fintech—is expanding quickly (Ema, 2007). RFL Electronics, a producer of electronic goods and one of the greatest employers in the nation besides the apparel sector, is a company in which we have investments. By producing these commodities domestically, it has been demonstrated that the domestic manufacturing base can become stronger and be made more accessible to consumers, thereby boosting consumption. In addition, as an investor and partner of RFL, we have been able to assist in the implementation of significant environmental and social reforms that can add genuine value to a company and support its aspirations to expand into worldwide markets (Watson, 2016).

Diversification of the economy has occurred beyond manufacturing. A little more than half of the country's GDP, or around 45%, is produced by the service sector, whereas 45% of Bangladeshis work in agriculture, where cotton and jute production is also common and rice is the most important crop (Radcliff, 2016). Opportunities exist for the country's developing service sector to

flourish, while other aspects of the economy, such as the requirement for infrastructure development, are impacted by the rise in population and GDP growth.

Though there is a great opportunity for investment, problems persist despite the recent advancements the nation has experienced. Despite a substantial rise in the past year, FDI still represents less than 1% of GDP, which the World Bank deemed insufficient in a development update report earlier this year. Bangladesh continues to have 37 million poor residents, 21 million of whom are in abject poverty (Monem, 2018). It's critical that there be a rise in the number of investors making long-term commitments to the market if development is to proceed at its current rate.

Investors are unable to commit to the long term due to a few important issues. The nation continues to fall behind, coming in at 176 out of 190 on the World Bank's Ease of Doing Business Index in 2018 (Faruk, 2019). For commercial investors, the dangerous market circumstances are additionally exacerbated by regulatory uncertainty, a lack of communication between regulatory agencies, and inconsistent policy implementation.

Progress of FDI in Bangladesh; Source : Business Standard

8.CONCLUSION

Bangladesh's economy is growing and its GDP is accelerating thanks in large part to FDI. Foreign direct investment has significantly contributed to Bangladesh's economy's modernization over the past 20 years. It supports the growth of the country's infrastructure, the expansion of employment opportunities, capacity building, the improvement of labor force skills through the exchange of management and technological know-how, and the blending of the local and global economies. Due to a number of its positive characteristics, Bangladesh is increasingly attracting investors from both established and developing countries (Ibteda, 2017). In Bangladesh, skilled professionals are inexpensive to hire. The macroeconomic environment is likewise rather stable. Bangladesh can be a suitable site for foreign investors due to these two essential factors. Bangladesh is a sought-after place for investments because of its cheap labor rates in comparison to other Asian countries, controlled inflation rate, relatively stable exchange rate (apart from the previous year), investment-friendly custom laws, and attractive incentive programs (Tansini, 2007). Bangladesh's foreign direct investment regulations have become more tax over the past few decades. The aforementioned factors would surely continue the foreign investors' FDI investment development in Bangladesh.

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10.1 Interview

No.	Name	Designation
1	Saleh Ahmed	Joint Secretary
2	Mr. Kouachi San	Managing Director, Sumitomo Corporation
3	Mrs. Umme	Office Manager, Sumitomo Corporation
4	Mazharul Islam	Deputy Manager
5	Opu	Utility business team leader